

ARTS

JEWELRY MASTERY IN TRAINING SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD OF FOLK-ART INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This article discusses the peculiarities of preparing future jewelers in the field of folk applied art. The issues, goals, tasks, and techniques that will help train a successful specialist in this area are considered.

Keywords: art, processing, metal, student, product, tradition

The course «Metal Jewelry Making» is designed for students of the «Decorative and Applied Arts» department who want to acquire special skills and abilities in making jewelry using filigree techniques. This involves various artistic metalworking techniques such as mounting work, filigree design, soldering, mechanical and chemical processing, stamping, engraving, and more [1, p.130].

To create or enchant, one must know the history of the item being made. Therefore, the process begins with gathering information from sources such as museums, exhibition halls, albums, books, journals, and reproductions.

The training of future specialists in this field aims to achieve the following objectives:

- to uncover the historical roots of artistic metalworking in the spiritual and material life of society;
- to develop artistic and creative abilities, including the ability to create original compositions within the traditions of artistic crafts of their region;
- to teach practical, traditional skills and techniques of artistic processing of different materials (in the third year, students make jewelry using various stones, and learn how to process them on-site).
- to study the technology and materials science of artistic metalworking, and to learn how to combine metal with wood, leather, etc. In order to develop the ability to independently create their compositions, students are introduced to the main concepts and patterns of composition in decorative and applied arts.

Starting from the first year, students copy samples, learn to creatively use the traditional elements of ornamentation, and vary and copy them in their own way, preserving their character and relying on the general visual content of the mood.

As A.V. Flerov said: «Masters and artists of applied arts working in the field of artistic metal must know, in addition to metals themselves, some related materials and techniques, such as hot enamel, blackening, precious and colored stones, their substitutes, etc. They must be able to use them easily, orient themselves

to know when and what to give preference to, what artistic effect can be achieved, etc.» [2, p.6].

The successful completion of the course «Metal Jewelry Making» is facilitated by a combination of lectures, practical classes, and individual lessons. It is important to note that all practical classes, as well as coursework in specialized artistic subjects, must be completed with high quality and attention to detail.

Proper attention should also be paid to questions of technology and decorating of products, formation of corresponding skills and abilities. Students should learn how to skillfully evaluate emerging changes in folk art, understand and interpret them correctly. Special attention should be paid to acquainting students with the artistic creativity of different peoples and their traditions. Only in this way can their artistic taste and aesthetic culture be purposefully formed.

In order to stimulate interest and love for decorative and applied arts, it is advisable to practice organizing and holding exhibitions of their works, encourage achievements, distinguish original, non-standard solutions.

The problem of aesthetic education is a problem of all humanity. In Kazakhstan, it is one of the main problems in connection with the revival of national, once rich traditions of applied art. Unfortunately, the state pays insufficient attention to this problem. Enthusiasts, people who care about their culture and art, solve it to the extent of their capabilities.

The revival and further development of folk arts and crafts, its progressive traditions and customs, is an urgent problem of modernity. Graduates of art universities play a special role in solving this issue.

The preparation of future specialists at M. Utemisov West Kazakhstan University is based on national-cultural traditions, where the curricula of artistic and creative disciplines reflect this orientation, special attention is focused on «folk arts and crafts» in the disciplines of the specialty.

Students specializing in «Artistic Processing of Metals and Other Materials» are direct heirs of the established ancient culture, traditions of folk art not only

of the West Kazakhstan region, but also of the entire decorative and applied art of Kazakhstan. They are expected to revive the once unjustly forgotten, rich national-cultural heritage of this region.

The solution to this problem in terms of training personnel for decorative and applied arts involves students mastering knowledge, skills, and abilities in the field of organizing folk arts and crafts enterprises. The final stage of the student's education is the diploma project. Its goal is to systematize, consolidate, and expand theoretical and practical knowledge in the specialty.

Work on the diploma project begins with the selection of a topic and before leaving for pre-diploma production practice, it is necessary to do significant work analyzing existing products, analogues, and prototypes. This will help identify the main shortcomings and find the optimal solution [3, p.182-183].

The future graduate approaches the diploma project with a certain program for organizing a folk arts and crafts enterprise. It should include questions of improving production organization management, increasing economic efficiency in specific sectors of the enterprise.

As future specialists and organizers of artistic production enterprises, graduates specializing in «Artistic

treatment of metals and other materials» must not only possess one of the types of art but also primarily be competent organizers of arts and crafts, planning material, technical, and personnel support for the industry.

During their education, students study a wide range of disciplines that contribute to their development and formation as highly qualified specialists. It is worth noting that education in an art university is particularly successful if the student has received prior professional training (in a studio, lyceum, or college). Then they are capable of solving complex creative tasks that our time presents to artists.

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